

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 837498.

SONNET – SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY TRANSITIONS

Co-creating a rich understanding of the diversity, processes, contributions, success and future potentials of social innovation in the energy sector

D7.5 | D30

Report on scientific conference participation, scientific publications and integration of SONNET results into training programmes

Project Coordinator: Fraunhofer ISI (Karoline Rogge)

Work Package: WP7 Co-creation and dissemination: Accelerating sustainable energy transitions

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Version: 1.1

May 2022

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GA#: 837498

Funding type: RIA

Deliverable number (relative in WP)	D7.5
Deliverable name:	Report on scientific conference participation, scientific publications and integration of SONNET results into training programmes
WP / WP number:	WP7
Delivery due date:	31 May 2022
Actual date of submission:	27 May 2022 (Update v1.1 May 31, 2022)
Dissemination level:	Public (PU)
Lead beneficiary:	SPRU, University of Sussex
Responsible scientist/administrator:	Ed Dearnley, SPRU
Contributor(s):	All SONNET partners
Internal reviewer(s):	Regina Betz (ZHAW), Sabine Hielscher (SPRU), Karoline Rogge (ISI)

PROJECT PARTNERS

No	Participant name	Short Name	Country code	Partners' logos
1	Fraunhofer Society, with its Fraunhofer Institute of Systems and Innovation Research (Fraunhofer ISI)	ISI	DE	Fraunhofer ISI
2	Dutch Research Institute for Transitions	DRIFT	NL	
3	University of Sussex, with its Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU)	UoS	UK	
4	Grenoble Ecole de Management	GEM	FR	
5	Akademia Leona Kozminkiego	ALK	PL	
6	Zurich University of Applied Sciences	ZHAW	CH	
7	ICLEI European Secretariat	ICLEI	DE	
8	City of Mannheim	MANN	GER	
9	City of Antwerp	ANTW	BE	
10	City of Bristol	BRIS	UK	
11	City of Grenoble	GREN	FR	
12	City of Warsaw	WARS	PL	
13	City of Basel (Associated Partner)	BASE	CH	

Executive Summary

SONNET deliverable D7.5 summarises the results of academic dissemination in the SONNET project, split into three distinct areas: scientific publications, presentations (and special sessions) at scientific conferences, and integration of SONNET results into training programmes. For these, **SONNET met or exceeded its targets.**

Twelve **scientific publications** have been published or accepted at the time of writing (exceeding the target of 10), with a large number of additional papers likely to be published after the formal end of the project. In addition, a SONNET special issue in the journal *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions* will be published later in 2022 (meeting the target).

Over thirty SONNET **conference presentations** (exceeding the target of 10) and six **special sessions** at academic events have been delivered at the time of writing (meeting the target of 6). This is something we can be particularly proud of considering the disruption presented by the COVID-19 pandemic, which meant travel restrictions were in place for much of the project. The SONNET team reacted by participating in online conferences, then beginning to switch back to in-person and hybrid events as restrictions loosened.

SONNET results have also been integrated into **teaching and training**, both as special one-off lectures and as case studies, etc. in ongoing programmes, as well as through supporting several MSc and PhD theses. The project had no formal target for this activity, but good progress has been made on delivering on this objective of significant teaching integration.

In common with most research projects, a large number of academic outputs will be delivered after the formal end of SONNET, as the research itself ends and the outputs are written up. SONNET's website will continue to be maintained for at least 3 years with an up-to-date list of academic publications and other outputs.

1 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

1.1 Journal Papers: Published and Planned

Publications in academic journals are a crucial, traditional route for disseminating research findings to academic audiences. In addition to the publications themselves, we can monitor metrics indicating the interest and/ or the impact of the publication, including:

- *Citations*. How many times the paper has been cited in other academic papers. Note that a paper's citations tend to grow slowly over a number of years – recently published papers are unlikely to have made many citations.
- *Tweeters*. The number of Twitter users tweeting about a paper. The majority of Tweets tend to come soon after a paper's publication and provide an immediate indication of the level of interest from both academia and the general public.
- *Mendeley Readers*. The number of users adding a paper to their Mendeley Library (an Elsevier product). This is a leading indicator for citations, i.e., users have been sufficiently interested in the paper to add it to their library and may therefore cite it in the future.

At the time of writing, SONNET has published nine journal papers, and a further three papers have been accepted for publication (but not yet published). These are summarised in Table 1 below.

As is common with most research projects, a significant number of papers are likely to be published after the formal end of the project. A list of planned papers is shown in Table 2, along with an indication of their current status. Note that not all of these papers will be published (as there is a risk of rejection) and titles may be subject to change. Also note that the author's names are not given in this table, as these papers may undergo a blind review process.

Performance against KPI

- *KPI*: 10 papers in scientific journals
- *Outturn*: 12 papers published or accepted at the time of writing in peer-reviewed scientific journals, with a significant number of additional papers at various stages of development

Table 1: SONNET Scientific Publications (Published or Accepted) as of May 2022

Paper	Authors	Journal	Date	Tweeters	Citations	Mendeley Readers
Beyond instrumentalism: Broadening the understanding of social innovation in socio-technical energy systems	Julia M. Wittmayer, Tessa de Geus, Bonno Pel, Flor Avelino, Sabine Hielscher, Thomas Hoppe, Susan Mühlemeier, Agata Stasik, Sem Oxenaar, Karoline S. Rogge, Vivian Visser, Esther Marín-González, Merel Ooms, Saskia Buitelaar, Chris Foulds, Kristian Petrick, Salvador Klarwein, Seweryn Krupnik, Gerdien de Vries, Aleksandra Wagner, Anja Härtwig	Energy Research & Social Science	Dec-20	64	18	154
Introduction: Action Research, Policy and Politics	Koen Bartels, Julia Wittmayer, Miren Larrea	International Journal of Action Research	Jan-21	1	1	7
Consumers or users? The impact of user learning about smart hybrid heat pumps on policy trajectories for heat decarbonisation	Bryony Parrish, Sabine Hielscher, Timothy J. Foxon	Energy Policy	Jan-21	0	2	22
Smart grids and institutional change: Emerging contestations between organisations over smart energy transitions	Friederike Rohde, Sabine Hielscher	Energy Research & Social Science	Apr-21	6	9	45

Paper	Authors	Journal	Date	Tweeters	Citations	Mendeley Readers
Who finances renewable energy in Europe? Examining temporality, authority and contestation in solar and wind subsidies in Poland, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom	Marfuga Iskandarova, Agata Dembek, Maria Fraaije, William Matthews, Agata Stasik, Julia M. Wittmayer, Benjamin K. Sovacool	Energy Strategy Reviews	Nov-21	0	1	36
Taking power seriously: Towards a power-sensitive approach for transdisciplinary action research	Marta Strumiński-Kutraa, Christian Scholl	Futures	Jan-22	10	1	19
Social movements in energy transitions: The politics of fossil fuel energy pathways in the United Kingdom, the Netherlands and Poland	Sabine Hielscher, Julia M. Wittmayer, Alicja Dańkowska	The Extractive Industries and Society	Apr-22	1	0	0
A typology for unpacking the diversity of social innovation in energy transitions	Julia M. Wittmayer, Sabine Hielscher, Maria Fraaije, Flor Avelino, Karoline Rogge	Energy Research & Social Science	Jun-22	2	0	28
Tangled transitions: Exploring the emergence of local electricity exchange in France, Switzerland and Great Britain	Marfuga Iskandarova, Anne-Lorène Vernay, Jörg Musiolik, Leticia Müller, Benjamin K. Sovacool	Technological Forecasting and Social Change	Jul-22	0	0	0
<i>Power and Empowerment in Social Innovation: Three Conceptual Frameworks</i>	<i>Flor Avelino, Julia Wittmayer, A. Dumitru</i>	<i>Book chapter: Howaldt, J. & C. Kaletka (eds) Encyclopedia of Social Innovation. Edward Elgar.</i>	<i>Accepted, not yet published</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>n/a</i>

Paper	Authors	Journal	Date	Tweeters	Citations	Mendeley Readers
<i>Soziale Innovationen in Transformationsprozessen - die Energiewende</i>	<i>Julia Wittmayer, Sabine Hielscher, Friederike Rohde, Karoline Rogge</i>	<i>Book chapter: Howaldt, J. & Streicher, J. (eds). Soziale Innovationen. Herausforderung für Politik und Wissenschaft. Campus</i>	<i>Accepted, not yet published</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>n/a</i>
<i>Social Innovation in Energy Transition: Evaluation Challenges and Innovative Solutions</i>	<i>Regina Betz, Christian Winzer</i>	<i>ECEEE Proceedings</i>	<i>Accepted, to be published June 2022</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>n/a</i>

Table 2: SONNET Scientific Publications in Progress

Status	Paper
Submitted, under review	How Can Transitions Theory account for the Dark Sides of Social Innovation?
Submitted, under review	Governing social innovation in energy on the city level: the process perspective
Submitted, under review	Policy mixes for social innovation? The case of participatory incubation and experimentation in energy in Germany
Submitted, under review	Making Sense of Power in Social Innovation in Energy Transitions: Insights from a Transformative Power Lab
Submitted, under review	Looking beyond the hype: conditions affecting the promise of behaviour change apps as social innovations for low-carbon transitions
Submitted, under review	Power to, over and with: exploring the transformative power of social innovations in energy transitions across Europe. Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions

Status	Paper
Submitted, under review	Fit for social innovation? Policy mix reflections for EU energy and climate policy making
Submitted, under review	Harnessing social innovation for accelerating sustainable and inclusive energy transitions
Work in progress	Comparison of energy cooperatives in Germany, France and Switzerland
Work in progress	Three Polish case studies and the dynamics of Polish energy transition
Work in progress	Impact of tracking CO ₂ -friendly behaviour in daily mobility and eating choices in a mobile phone app
Work in progress	Governing Social Innovation in energy. Moving between logics of market, hierarchies and networks
Work in progress	How energy communities can contribute to energy transition? Lessons learnt from France
Work in progress	Paper on cities for a special issue on "Vital Cities: Unleashing the Vitality of Residents" for Cities: The International Journal of Urban Policy and Planning.
Work in progress	Evaluating a city lab process in Mannheim's district Neckarstadt-West: Three main challenges for the evaluation (conference paper)
Work in progress	Understanding citizen investment in renewable energy cooperatives: insight from a discrete choice experiment in three countries
Work in progress	Scaling up: evaluating the potential of energy cooperatives in France
Work in progress	A discrete choice experiment on mobile energy apps in Germany
Work in progress	Citizen perception of campaigns against coal in Poland: Insights from two online experiments
Work in progress	Special Issue Introduction: Advancing the understanding of social innovation in sustainability transitions: Potentials, processes, and policies for accelerating transitions.

Spotlight: Beyond instrumentalism: Broadening the understanding of social innovation in socio-technical energy systems

'Beyond instrumentalism' was SONNET's first scientific publication, published in *Energy Research and Social Science* in December 2020. The paper explores social innovation in the energy transition. Existing viewpoints tend to perceive social innovation as a simple instrument to achieve energy transition aims. The SONNET paper argues for a more holistic approach, stressing how energy systems are embedded in broader systems-of-systems, and intertwined with multiple societal issues and practices. Social innovation in energy transitions can therefore be an opportunity for addressing multiple social issues, or even rethinking society as a whole.

To date, the paper has been cited 16 times. It also received significant Twitter interest on publication, towards the end of 2020. Altmetric – a service tracking online interest in academic publications – currently gives the paper an 'attention score' of 46, which puts it in the top 5% of all scientific publications.

Figure 1: Two tweets mentioning the 'Beyond Instrumentalism' paper

1.2 SONNET Special Issue on Social Innovation

The SONNET team made a successful proposal for a special issue on social innovation in the journal *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions (EIST)*, with the working title 'Advancing the understanding of social innovation in sustainability transitions: Potentials, processes, and policies for accelerating transitions'. The special issue has two aims. Firstly, it provides a single, high-profile publication for the SONNET team to publish some of its research. Secondly, it amplifies the work of SONNET by soliciting publications on the social innovation theme from outside of the SONNET team.

A three-day workshop was held in November 2021 as part of the editorial process, and the final submission deadline closed in April 2022. The special issue itself will be published later in 2022, after the end of the SONNET project.

Performance against KPI

- *KPI*: 1 special issue about social innovation in energy
- *Outturn*: 1 special issue scheduled for publication in EIST

2 CONFERENCE PRESENTATIONS AND SPECIAL CONFERENCE SESSIONS

Despite the pandemic travel restrictions in place for much of the project, SONNET partners still managed to make a large number of presentations at academic conferences. In addition, special sessions – focusing on SONNET themes – were held at a number of high-profile scientific events.

2.1 Conference Presentations

Presentations from the SONNET team at academic conferences are detailed in Table 3 below, whilst Table 4 provides information on conference presentations planned after the formal end of the project. You will note the shift to online events from 2020, and a shift back to in-person and hybrid events from 2021, due to the evolution of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Performance against KPI

- *KPI*: 10 conference presentations
- *Outturn*: 33 conference presentations given

Figure 2: Karoline Rogge presenting at the European School of Social Innovation (ESSI) Conference 2019

Table 3: SONNET Academic Conference Presentations as of May 2022

Title	Conference	Location	Date	Presenter	Partner
Towards a broad understanding of social innovation in energy	International Social Innovation Research Conference ISIRC 2019	Glasgow, UK	3 September 2019	Julia Wittmayer, Sabine Hielscher	DRIFT
Transformative digital social innovation					
Towards an analytical framework for capturing the role and impact of social innovations in energy transitions					
Bridging social innovation and policy mix research: an exploration for the case of social innovation in energy transitions	5th Global Research Conference Social Innovation and Socio-Digital Transformation: Towards a Comprehensive Innovation Policy (ESSI)	Dortmund, Germany	28-29 October 2019	Karoline Rogge	Fraunhofer ISI
In which themes is mission orientation relevant? Sustainability and Energy (in German)	Mission-oriented innovation policy, Evangelische Akademie Loccum	Online	16-17 June 2020	Karoline Rogge	Fraunhofer ISI
Towards power sensitive concept of Post Normal Science	5th Post Normal Science Symposium	Online	21-25 September 2020	Marta Strumińska-Kutra	Kozminski University (ALK)
Transformative policy mixes for accelerating sustainability transitions in the energy sector (keynote talk)	11th International Sustainability Transition conference (IST)	Online	18-21 August 2021	Karoline Rogge	Fraunhofer ISI
Mapping the diverse roles of the city in shaping the conditions for social innovation in energy transitions – first empirical insights (parallel session speed talk)				Maria Stadler, Heike Brugger	

Title	Conference	Location	Date	Presenter	Partner
Urban spaces in transition(s) - a socio-spatial perspective on new ways of doing, thinking, organising urban spaces in the course of sustainability transitions.	Workshop of the working group 'interdisciplinary urban research' at TU Darmstadt	Online	18 March 2021	Maria Stadler	Fraunhofer ISI
Social Innovation Scaling Patterns in different Institutional Contexts: The case of Energy cooperatives in France, Germany, and Switzerland	BEHAVE 2020-2021	Copenhagen	23 April 2021	Adélie Ranville	GEM
Urban spaces in transition(s) - new ways of doing, thinking, organising urban spaces in the course of sustainability transitions	NEST Conference 2021	Sofia, Bulgaria	8-9 April 2021	Maria Stadler	Fraunhofer ISI
Institutionalization processes of social innovation fields in the energy sector: European countries case studies	COMETS Mid-Term Conference and EERA e3s Joint Programme event	Online	20 May 2021	Ranville, A., B. Schmid, J. Heidary	GEM
How successfully do SIE-initiatives contribute to EU policy goals?	Energieforschungsgespräche Disentis	Online	21 January 2021	Christian Winzer	ZHAW
Cooperation with Incumbents in Scaling Strategies of Energy Cooperatives in France, Germany, and Switzerland: Indispensable Synergies or Faustian Bargain?				Benjamin Schmidt, Adélie Ranville	
Car ride or beef sandwich? Impact of tracking CO ₂ -friendly behaviour in daily mobility and eating choices in a mobile phone app	ECEEE 2021	Online	11 June 2021	Devon Wemyss	ZHAW

Title	Conference	Location	Date	Presenter	Partner
Challenging science and society? Exploring research relations in coproduction spaces	Interpretive Policy Analysis Conference #13: Interpreting Politics, Governance and Space	Online	28 June 2021	Julia Wittmayer	DRIFT
Framings against fossil-fuel energy pathways: A comparison of social innovation in energy fields in the Netherlands (UK, Poland)			1 July 2021	Julia Wittmayer, Sabine Hielscher, Ala Dankowska	DRIFT, SPRU, ALK
SONNET & the diversity of social innovation in energy transitions (SIE)	Lunch lecture @Sozialforschungsstelle Dortmund, Germany	Online	18 May 2021	Julia Wittmayer, Karoline Rogge	DRIFT and Fraunhofer ISI
Unpacking the Diversity of Social Innovation in Energy Transitions	International Social Innovation Research Conference ISIRC 2021	Online	8 September 2021	Julia Wittmayer, Maria Fraaije, Sabine Hielscher	DRIFT, SPRU
Questioning Power in Social Innovations in Energy Transitions: Insights from a Transformative Power Lab.	International Social Innovation Research Conference ISIRC 2021		8 September 2021	Flor Avelino, Tessa de Geus, Sabine Hielscher	DRIFT, SPRU
Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways: A comparison of social innovation in energy in the United Kingdom, Poland and the Netherlands	12th International Sustainability Transitions Conference - IST 2021	Online	5-8 October 2021	Julia Wittmayer, Sabine Hielscher	DRIFT, SPRU
Social Movements, Sustainability Transitions and Social Innovation				Flor Avelino	DRIFT
Governing social innovation in energy on the city level: the process perspective				Marta Strumińska-Kutra	ALK, ISI, SPRU

Title	Conference	Location	Date	Presenter	Partner
How can policy networks enable social innovation in energy? A comparative analysis				Iska Brunzema	Fraunhofer ISI
Making Sense of Power in Social Innovation in Energy Transitions: Insights from a Transformative Power Lab				Tessa de Geus	DRIFT, ALK, SPRU, ISI
Policy mixes promoting social innovation? Lessons learned from a cross-case and cross-country comparison of social innovation in energy transitions				Karoline Rogge	Fraunhofer ISI, SPRU, DRIFT
Reflections on Transformative Innovation Policy from a Transformative Policy Mix Perspective	Eu-SPRI 2021 – Early Career Research Conference (ECC)	Paris and Online	21 October 2021	Karoline Rogge	Fraunhofer ISI
Keynote presentation on "Social innovation in energy: Transforming energy systems?"	SIET-conference on "Social innovation: next steps in the energy transition conference", TU Delft	Online	19 November 2021	Julia Wittmayer	DRIFT
Transformative policy mixes for social innovation? Lessons learned from case studies of social innovation in energy transitions (Panel „Policies And Institutions For Social Innovations In Renewable Energy Transitions“)				Karoline Rogge	Fraunhofer ISI
Drivers and barriers to citizen investment in renewable electricity generation projects	Energy Research Talks Disentis 2022	Online	28 Jan 2022	Marie Charlotte Guetlein	GEM
Looking inside: Capability Approach and Social Innovation	ESSI Webinar: Quo Vadis? A Research Agenda for Social Innovation	Online	5 April 22	Julia Wittmayer	DRIFT

Title	Conference	Location	Date	Presenter	Partner
Shifting Power Relations in Sustainability Transitions: A Multi-actor Perspective	Share your knowledge day at the Erasmus University	Online	4 April 22	Julia Wittmayer	DRIFT
Dialogic organizing for value transparency science-policy communication.	16th Organization Studies Workshop Dialogic organizing: Affirming public engagement for hope and solidarity	Chania, Greece	19-21 May 2022	Marta Strumińska-Kutra	Kozminski University (ALK)

Table 4: SONNET Academic Conference Presentations Planned After May 2022

Conference	Location	Date	Presenter	Partner
ECEEE summer study	Hyerres, France	6-10 June 2022	Regina Betz, Devon Wemyss	ZHAW
EAERE	Rimini, Italy	28 June-1 July 2022	Marie-Charlotte, Joachim	GEM

In addition to formal conference presentations, the SONNET team also presented findings at smaller invited seminars and research briefings, for example at Cambridge University, LUND University, and ETH Zurich. We have not listed these smaller events nor counted them against our KPIs.

2.2 Special Conference Sessions

Special conference sessions include activities such as panel sessions and workshops, themed around a particular topic. SONNET arranged several special sessions themed around the project's work, with presenters and participants from both the project team and outside of SONNET. These are detailed in Table 5 below.

Performance against KPI

- *KPI*: 6 special sessions.
- *Outturn*: 6 special sessions arranged (plus one special conference track co-organised).

Table 5: SONNET Special Conference Sessions as of May 2022

Title	Conference	Location	Date	Organisers	Partner(s)
Is energy efficiency (fe)male? The role of gender for sustainable energy use (Format: panel discussion)	6th European Conference on Energy Efficiency and Behaviour Change	Online	21-23 April 2021	Elisabeth Dütschke, Sabine Preuß	Fraunhofer ISI
Narratives, frames and knowledge in the current energy and climate debate	Interpretive Policy Analysis Conference #13: Interpreting Politics, Governance and Space	Online	29 June 2021	Julia Wittmayer, Sabine Hielscher	DRIFT and SPRU
Managing through crises in urban transdisciplinary research settings (Format: dialogue session)	12th International Sustainability Transitions Conference - IST 2021	Online (Karlsruhe)	5-8 October 2021	Agata Dembek, Agata Stasik, Marta Strumińska-Kutra, Niklas Mischkowski	ALK and ICLEI

Title	Conference	Location	Date	Organisers	Partner(s)
Social movements and sustainability transitions: Matters of democracy, power and institutional change?	12th International Sustainability Transitions Conference - IST 2021	Online	5-8 October 2021	Sabine Hielscher, Julia Wittmayer	SPRU and DRIFT
Governing energy transitions through social innovation? Unpacking the role of power, policy networks and policy mixes.	12th International Sustainability Transitions Conference - IST 2021	Online	5-8 October 2021	Karoline Rogge	Fraunhofer ISI
Social Innovation in Energy Transition (4 Sister Projects presented their findings of large surveys)	Energy Research Talks, Disentis 2022	Switzerland and online	28 January 2022	Regina Betz, Devon Wemyss	ZHAW and GEM

In addition, SONNET team members Karoline Rogge (ISI) and Sabine Hielscher (SPRU) have co-organised a Special Conference Track on “Transformative Social Innovation in Sustainability and Health” at the EuSPRI Forum, Utrecht, NL, June 1-3, 2022, thereby supporting the lead organiser Tineke Kleinhout-Vliek, Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Utrecht.

Spotlight: Special Sessions at the International Sustainability Transitions (IST) Conference, 2021

At IST 2021, SONNET held two panel sessions and a dialogue session. These sessions featured the work of SONNET partners, and also that of academic colleagues from outside of SONNET, who presented their work on similar themes. The special sessions allowed us to draw greater attention to the project (when compared to a standard paper presentation), and also engage more closely with academics working in complementary fields.

The slide features a purple-to-orange gradient background. At the top center is the SONNET logo. Below it, the text reads "Join SONNET at the 12th International Sustainability Transitions Conference (IST 2021)". Two calendar icons are positioned below the text. The first icon is for 6.10.2021, with a session from 10:45–12:15 (paper session). The second icon is for 7.10.2021, with sessions from 9:00–10:30 (special session), 9:00–10:30 (dialogue session), and 10:45–12:15 (special session). At the bottom center, a URL is provided: <https://www.ist2021-karlsruhe.de/>

Figure 3: Overview slide for SONNET at IST 2021

The slide has a purple-to-orange gradient background. At the top left, it states "Special session at the International Sustainability Transitions Conference 2021 hosted by Fraunhofer ISI Thursday, October 7, 2021, 10:45 – 12:15 CET". At the top right is the "Social Innovation in Energy Transitions" logo. The main title is "Governing energy transitions through social innovation? Unpacking the role of power, policy networks and policy mixes". Below this is a list of four presentations:

1. Marta Strumińska-Kutra, Agata Dembek, Sabine Hielscher and Maria Stadler: *Governing social innovation in energy on the city level: the process perspective*
2. Iska Brunzema, Maria Stadler and Heike Brugger: *How can policy networks enable social innovation in energy? A comparative analysis*
3. Tessa de Geus, Flor Avelino, Marta Strumińska-Kutra, Julia Wittmayer, Lara Hendrikx, Karoline Rogge and Sabine Hielscher: *Making Sense of Power in Social Innovation in Energy Transitions: Insights from a Transformative Power Lab*
4. Karoline Rogge, Maria Stadler, Sabine Hielscher, Maria Fraije and Julia Wittmayer: *Policy mixes promoting social innovation? Lessons learned from a cross-case and cross-country comparison of social innovation in energy transitions*

At the bottom left is the European Union flag logo. At the bottom center, a small text reads: "The SONNET project organising this special session has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 837468."

Figure 4: Holding slide for one of SONNET's IST 2021 special sessions

3 INTEGRATION OF SONNET RESULTS INTO TRAINING PROGRAMMES

One of SONNET's innovative aims was to integrate the results of the project into teaching and training. This can take a number of different forms, for example the outputs of the project can feature in lectures, etc, and/or aspects of the project can be used as case studies for the application of research techniques used in SONNET. We also integrated a number of PhD and MSc thesis into the project, using SONNET as a launch pad for new researchers.

Table 6 shows teaching and training activities delivered at the time of writing, whilst Table 7 shows activities planned for delivery after the formal end of the project.

There is no formal KPI for this activity.

Table 6: Teaching and training activities integrating SONNET materials as of May 2022

Type of activity	Course, Lecture, etc.	Title	Date	Organiser	Partner(s)
Academic teaching	Lecture	Lecture for students of higher education	15 September 2020	Julia Wittmayer	DRIFT
Academic teaching	Module at the Postdoc Academy for Transformational Leadership (Transition Academy)	Dilemmas, roles and capacities in action and transdisciplinary research	12 November 2020	Julia Wittmayer	DRIFT
Academic teaching	Lecture for the Minor course Science & Practice for Transformative Change	Transformative Research and the role of researchers	30 October 2020	Julia Wittmayer	DRIFT
Academic training	Lecture on policy mixes for NEST webinar	Policy Mixes for Sustainability Transitions	23 July 2020	Karoline Rogge	Fraunhofer ISI
Training	Training	Energy Champion volunteers trained to recruit community organisations	17 November 2020	Bristol Energy Network	Bristol City Council

Type of activity	Course, Lecture, etc.	Title	Date	Organiser	Partner(s)
Academic teaching	Course on social innovation in Energy (Specialised course given to GEM students)	Social innovation in Energy (3h)	3 June 2021	Anne-Lorène Vernay	GEM
Academic teaching	Lecture at the EGSH graduate school PhD course on Participatory Action Research	Action-oriented research and the role of researchers	18 May 2021	Julia Wittmayer	DRIFT
Academic teaching	Bachelor thesis by Lukas Schoch on the Basel city lab	Eine Analyse wie die Nutzung einer Smartphone-App das Verhalten und den Wissensstand zum CO ₂ -Fussabdruck verändert	5 July 2021	Manuel Grieder	ZHAW
Academic teaching	Lecture for students	Social innovation in the Energy Transition - case study from practice	15 September 2021	Julia Wittmayer	DRIFT
Academic teaching	MSc thesis	The role of intermediaries for social innovation in the German energy transition. An empirical analysis of energy cooperatives in Germany	02 November 2021	Jasmin Heidary	Fraunhofer ISI
Academic teaching	Lecture for students	Transformative Research and the roles of researchers	10 November 2021	Julia Wittmayer	DRIFT
Academic training	PhD Thesis	The role of digital and social innovation on improving individual energy use	30 March 2022	Devon Wemyss	SPRU
Academic teaching	MSc thesis	Power structures and trust as an obstacle to innovation.	30 March 2022	Iska Brunzema	Fraunhofer ISI

Type of activity	Course, Lecture, etc.	Title	Date	Organiser	Partner(s)
Practitioner training	Video training	Les coopératives d'énergie en Suisse, France et Allemagne : comment diffuser un modèle alternatif dans un secteur complexe ?	March 2022	Adélie Ranville	GEM
Training	Internship	Internship, predominantly contributing to WP2	Nov. 2021 – Feb. 2022	Annalena Broich	Fraunhofer ISI
Academic teaching	Lecture	Course on Sustainable Development (BA) at ALK	22 April 2022	Agata Dembek	ALK
Academic teaching	Certificate of Advanced Studies	Climate strategies	March 2022 – January 2023	Regina Betz	ZHAW
Academic teaching	Executive teaching (Module)	Masterclass Versnelling Energietransitie	19 May 2022	Julia Wittmayer	DRIFT
Training	Executive training with Polish Cities (informal group, resulting from SONNET on tour)	Miasta w transformacji	23 March 2022	Agata Stasik	ALK
Academic training	PhD Thesis	Working title: Cities' roles in transition(s) - new ways of thinking, doing, organizing urban governance in the course of sustainability transitions	Ongoing	Maria Stadler	Fraunhofer ISI
Academic training	PhD Thesis	Working title: Energy cooperatives in France	Ongoing	Adélie Ranville	GEM
Academic training	PhD Thesis	A multi-level perspective on the Polish energy transition: managing social innovation development towards systemic change	Ongoing	Alicja Dańkowska	ALK

Table 7: Planned teaching and training activities integrating SONNET materials after May 2022

Type of activity	Course, Lecture, etc.	Title	Anticipated Date	Organiser	Partner(s)
Academic teaching	MSc Programme	New Master Program on Sustainable Transitions (ALK); starts in the upcoming academic year	September 2022	Agata Dembek	ALK
Academic teaching	Academic teaching (Lecture)	PhD Course Introduction to action-oriented research for social change	Multiple	Julia Wittmayer	DRIFT
Academic teaching	Academic teaching (Lecture)	PhD Course EUSPRI Social Innovation Policy: Concepts, Methods and Policy Practices	21-23 September 2022	Julia Wittmayer	DRIFT
Academic teaching	Academic teaching (Lecture)	PhD Course Methods for Sustainability Transitions Research: Mixed Methods	6 September 2022	Julia Wittmayer	DRIFT

Spotlight: Integration of SONNET case studies into academic lectures

The DRIFT team has lectured extensively on action research and transdisciplinary research, using the SONNET Antwerp case study as an example. Using the SONNET case studies in this way helps to bring education around research techniques to life, showing students not just the theoretical use of techniques, but how they have actually been used in practice and the results they have generated.

drift for transition

City Labs: to support energy transitions locally

Social INNOvation in Energy Transitions

 WARSAW Addressing energy efficiency governance	 MANNHEIM Speeding up the local energy transition	 GRENOBLE Addressing energy consumption
 BRISTOL Addressing energy retrofitting/financing	 BASEL Addressing energy consumption	 ANTWERP Addressing energy poverty

Supporting learning processes in addressing societal challenges through reflexive monitoring

drift for transition

GelijkStroom

Reflexive Monitoring with Antwerp

~01/2020 – 07/2021

City: Antwerp aims to use social innovation for a just energy transitions: creating new networks in the city, learning about social innovation and the role of the city in a just energy transition, integrating learning in institutions

Research: How, and under which circumstances can urban labs result in new breakthrough and address barriers faced by local energy transition dynamics?

Learning by doing through four experiments & reflexive monitoring (field diaries, learning sessions, ...)

Social INNOvation in Energy Transitions

Reflexive Monitoring in Action
A guide for monitoring social innovation projects

Figure 5: Examples of lecture slides used by the DRIFT team

4 APPENDIX 1: EC SUMMARY REQUIREMENTS

Changes with respect to the DoA

There are no changes with respect to the DoA.

Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable describes the results of academic dissemination activities.

Short Summary of results

The SONNET project aimed to disseminate its results to an academic audience via academic journal papers, conference presentations, special sessions and integration into teaching programmes. As of May 2022, the project had delivered 12 journal papers (published and accepted), 32 conference presentations, 6 special sessions and 19 teaching integration activities. A significant number of further papers, presentations and teaching activities will also take place after the formal end of the project.

Evidence of accomplishment

This deliverable.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 837498.